

Hiring Only AACSB-School Graduates: Some Economic, Legal and Ethical Problems

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JEL Code: K31, I21, M4, D61

Abstract

The American Assembly of Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB) is the elite organization that accredits business schools in the United States. Many of its "policies" are of questionable value, but we will only touch on that topic in this article.

The main thrust of this article will be a hiring practice at business schools that has become disturbingly all too frequent. In the employment ads that some business schools run to recruit accounting and other business professors, there has been a disturbing trend toward considering only graduates of AACSB accredited institutions. There are several economic, legal and ethical problems with such a policy. The author discusses these problems.

Introduction

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The main thrust of this article will be a hiring practice at business schools that has become disturbingly all too frequent. In

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the employment ads that some business schools run to recruit accounting and other business professors, there has been a disturbing trend toward considering only graduates of AACSB accredited institutions.² There are several economic, legal and ethical problems with such a policy.

Economic Problems

A major economic problem with hiring only AACSB-school graduates is that there aren't too many of them. Only 38 people received PhDs in accounting in 1997, which was a big decline from the 142 that were awarded the previous year.³ Since the supply is artificially crimped by excluding the graduates of the many other good schools that turn out potential accounting professors, the price is artificially increased. If there were adequate justification for excluding a large number of qualified professors, perhaps the premium that schools have to pay to get AACSB-school graduates would be worth the cost. But it is not.

Which brings us to the second major economic problem. Do schools that hire AACSB-school graduates get their moneysworth? Let's look at the PhD program requirements of one of the top accounting PhD programs.⁴ One would think that accounting PhD programs prepare people to teach accounting. But a look at the degree requirements makes one think twice about that assumption.

² I know of one individual who had 8 doctorates and hundreds of publications who was refused an interview because none of his doctorates were from AACSB-accredited schools.

³ JAMES R. HASSELBACK, PRENTICE HALL 1998-1999 ACCOUNTING FACULTY DIRECTORY (1998). Statistics on PhD graduates is given in the front part of the book, two pages before page one.

⁴ I will not disclose the name of the school because I do not want to embarrass the faculty members who teach there. However, this school has produced the third highest number of accounting PhDs of all the schools listed in the Hasselback (1998) book.

The PhD program must include either a minor in financial economics or behavioral science. We will examine the financial economics track. Here are the requirements:

Year 1:

Fall

Accounting Seminar - 1
ECON 370: Quantitative Economics
STAT 385: Regression

Spring

Accounting Seminar - 2
SOC 431: Multivariate Methods
ECON 472: Econometrics I

Summer

Work on first-year research project

Year 2:

Fall

Accounting Seminar - 3
ECON 405: Microeconomics
FIN 403: Corporate Finance

Spring

FIN 405-1: Theory of Financial Economics I
FIN 435: Investments
Elective in finance, economics or statistics

Summer

Accounting Seminar - 4

Year 3:

Fall

ECON 473: Econometrics II
Electives in finance, economics or statistics

Spring

ACCT 491: Dissertation Research

Summer

ACCT 491: Dissertation Research

Year 4:**Fall**

ACCT 491: Dissertation Research

Spring

ACCT 491: Dissertation Research

Summer

ACCT 491: Dissertation Research

Defend dissertation

With the exception of the four accounting seminars, students are not allowed to take any coursework in accounting whatsoever. Only 4 of the 16 courses can be in accounting.⁵ That's 25 percent. If one counts the research requirement, the amount of work that prepares students to teach accounting is even less than that, since the research requirement does nothing to add to classroom teaching skills, and often adds no content knowledge either. It makes one question whether calling this program a program in accounting constitutes false advertising.

Legal Problems

Schools that advertise that they will hire or prefer only AACSB-school graduates face potential legal problems. In order to not be accused of discrimination, there has to be a good reason for excluding certain groups. Excluding non-AACSB graduates might constitute a suspect classification under the Fourteenth Amendment. That means they have to justify their policy or face potential discrimination lawsuits. Based on the above analysis, it appears that they will be hard pressed to defend such a policy, since schools that have AACSB-accredited accounting PhD programs do not offer much value. It would be difficult to justify restricting recruitment to AACSB-school graduates if AACSB schools have accounting programs that offer 25 percent or less of their program in accounting, especially if some non-AACSB

⁵ The 12 nonaccounting courses assumes 2 electives in the fall of the third year.

schools have a higher percentage of accounting in their accounting programs.

Another related legal problem involves the Disparate Impact Doctrine. This doctrine had its origins in *Griggs v. Duke Power Co.*, a 1971 Supreme Court case that held that barriers to equal employment opportunity can exist even if an employment policy is neutral on its face, provided the policy has a disparate impact on some protected group. If disparate impact is found, the burden shifts to the employer to prove that there is no discriminatory intent. This ruling was later modified by *Wards Cove Packing Co. v. Antonio*⁶ and again modified by Title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1991.⁷

Since it is mostly the elite schools that are AACSB accredited, and since minorities probably attend (and graduate from) elite schools less frequently than non-elite schools, a case can be made that any rule that restricts hiring to graduates of AACSB-accredited schools is discriminatory.

Ethical Problems

Aside from the possibility that a policy of hiring or giving preference to individuals who graduated from AACSB-accredited doctoral programs might be discriminatory, there are other

⁶ *Wards Cove Packing Co. v. Antonio*, 490 US 642 (1989).

⁷ For more on the Disparate Impact Doctrine, see Linda Lye, *Title VII's tangled tale: The erosion and confusion of disparate impact and the business necessity defense*, 19 *BERKELEY JOURNAL OF EMPLOYMENT AND LABOR LAW* 315-361 (1998); Rosemary C. Hunter and Elaine W. Shoben, *Disparate impact discrimination: American oddity or internationally accepted concept?* 19 *BERKELEY JOURNAL OF EMPLOYMENT AND LABOR LAW* 108-152 (1998); Peter E. Mahoney, *The end(s) of disparate impact: Doctrinal reconstruction, fair housing and lending law, and the antidiscrimination principle*, 47 *EMORY LAW JOURNAL* 409-525 (1998); Larry Alexander and Kevin Cole, *Discrimination by proxy*, 14 *CONSTITUTIONAL COMMENTARY* 453-463 (Winter 1997); Raymond L. Hogler, Christine Henle and Carol Bemus, *Internet recruiting and employment discrimination: A legal perspective*, *HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT REVIEW* 149-164 (Summer 1998).

potential ethical problems. Although private schools should be allowed to establish any hiring criteria they want regardless of how stupid it may be,⁸ state schools do not have this flexibility. They have an extra responsibility not to favor some groups over others because they are supposed to treat all groups and all individuals equally.

There is also the ethical question of fiduciary responsibility. Educational institutions have a duty to hire the best people they can find.⁹ Their students are paying tuition to receive a good education and colleges and universities have an obligation to give them value for their money.¹⁰ Universities and colleges often disregard this ethical duty, however. Policies that artificially

⁸ Another major issue, which we will not discuss in this article, is whether private institutions should be able to establish whatever policies they want even if those policies might be discriminatory. In other words, is there a right to private discrimination? For discussions of this issue, see Robert W. McGee, *Should Private Discrimination Constitute an Act Discreditable to the Profession? A Philosophical Look at a Practical Ethical Question*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Fall 1998), forthcoming; Robert W. McGee, *The Right Not To Associate: The Case for an Absolute Freedom of Negative Association*, 23 UNIVERSITY OF WEST LOS ANGELES LAW REVIEW 123-148 (1992).

⁹ Many university officials are probably unaware of this duty, based on the policies at most schools, but that is a topic for another article.

¹⁰ If a free market existed in higher education, the market would sort out this problem. Those schools that offer an inferior product for the money would eventually have to either close their doors, reform or reduce the price they charge. However, there is not a free market in higher education. Accreditation requirements greatly reduce the possibility for innovation because they all have to offer programs that are structurally about the same. Students who want to get a bachelors degree in accounting, for example, must take about 75 percent of the coursework required for a degree in courses other than accounting. They may not shop around for a school that allows them to take a higher percentage in accounting because accreditation "standards" will not allow a school to offer such consumer-oriented programs. In a free market, schools would be able to offer programs that consisted of 100 percent accounting courses if there were a demand for such programs. For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Let's Have More Choice in Accounting Education*, forthcoming.

limit potential faculty members to those who have a PhD¹¹ or who publish, or who are members of some protected group, for example, all place artificial crimps in the supply of otherwise available professors. Thus, the quality of the professorate is suboptimal. A policy of hiring only AACSB-school graduates increases this suboptimality without adding any value. Thus, a case can be made that a policy of hiring only AACSB-school graduates is unethical.

Concluding Comments

It has been shown that a policy of hiring or giving preference to AACSB-school graduates is uneconomical. It places an artificial crimp in the supply, which leads to a corresponding increase in cost, without any corresponding benefits. There are also potential legal problems with the policy. The policy is also unethical, not only because it is discriminatory but also because it involves a breach of fiduciary duty. Colleges and universities that have such a policy should abandon it immediately, not only because it is economically inefficient and potentially a legal problem, but also because abandoning such policies is the ethically right thing to do.

¹¹ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Do Accounting Educators Need a PhD?*, forthcoming; Robert W. McGee, *The Case for a Nonresearch Doctorate in Accounting*, forthcoming; Robert W. McGee, *Eliminate the PhD Requirement for Accounting Educators*, *MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING* 58, 61 (April 1986).